

Affordable Sorting Validation for Accessible Stem Cell Therapy (DEPCELL)

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan covers the data, software, AI models, analysis scripts, reports and metadata generated in the DEPCELL project. The project validates a label-free dielectrophoresis (DEP) sorting approach for viable adipose-derived mesenchymal stromal cells (AD-MSCs) linked to telomere status, combined with AI-enabled quality control under GMP-like conditions to support accessible stem cell therapy under the Hospital Exemption pathway. Experimental data will be documented in standardised formats, stored in controlled RTU environments, and non-sensitive outputs will be made openly available in line with FAIR principles.

Funder

Funding Organization

Grant

Grant

Researchers

Janis Baronins (0000-0002-0831-2733), Uldis Berzins (0009-0003-1996-3894), Aija Rautmane (0000-0002-2293-0837), Veranika Khlud (0000-0002-0732-6463)

Organizations
Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Affordable Sorting Validation for Accessible Stem Cell Therapy \(DEPCELL\)](#)

Description:

This Data Management Plan covers the data, software, AI models, analysis scripts, reports and metadata generated in the DEPCELL project. The project validates a label-free dielectrophoresis (DEP) sorting approach for viable adipose-derived mesenchymal stromal cells (AD-MSCs) linked to telomere status, combined with AI-enabled quality control under GMP-like conditions to support accessible stem cell therapy under the Hospital Exemption pathway. Experimental data will be documented in standardised formats, stored in controlled RTU environments, and non-sensitive outputs will be made openly available in line with FAIR principles.

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[Riga Technical University](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Funding Organization](#)

Grants: [Grant](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

DEPCELL experimental, AI and validation data

This Description covers the main research data generated in the DEPCELL project during validation of a label-free DEP-based stem-cell sorting platform for adipose-derived mesenchymal stromal cells (AD-MSC). It includes experimental laboratory data, cell characterisation and quality-control results, telomere-related analytical data, AI-assisted microscopy outputs, analysis scripts, metadata, validation protocols and technical reports. The purpose of these data is to support technology validation from TRL3 to TRL4-5, document reproducible research workflows, and enable future scientific re-use of non-sensitive datasets and software in line with FAIR principles.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data will be collected and generated to validate a label-free dielectrophoresis (DEP) cell-sorting workflow for adipose-derived mesenchymal stromal cells (AD-MSCs), link DEP fingerprints to telomere length and replicative status, and support AI-assisted quality control under GMP-like conditions. The data directly support the project's objective to advance the RTU prototype from TRL3 to TRL4-5, generate validation evidence across at least eight donors/patients, and prepare the technology for Hospital Exemption (ATMP/HE) use. Data originate from in-house laboratory experiments (DEP, flow cytometry/Flow-FISH, microscopy, migration, senescence, potency and safety testing), anonymised survey/market-research activities, software/code generation, and associated documentation and reports.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Machine-readable text
- Experimental data
- Textual data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- JPG
- Others

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The core DEPCELL dataset will be newly generated during the project. External literature and, where relevant, public reference data may be used for contextual comparison or benchmarking only.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data may be useful to researchers in dielectrophoresis, mesenchymal stromal cell biology, telomere and senescence research, GMP-like cell manufacturing, AI-enabled microscopy and QC, lab-on-chip development and translational ATMP research. It may also be useful to clinicians, Hospital Exemption providers,

regulators and technology-transfer/commercialisation stakeholders interested in accessible cell therapy workflows.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

Search keywords will be provided for all public datasets and documentation. Keywords will combine controlled biomedical terminology with project-specific technical terms to improve discoverability and re-use.

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

Version numbers will be provided for datasets, code, AI models, protocols and documentation. Raw, cleaned, analysed and published versions will be distinguished clearly.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

A limited embargo of up to 12 months after project end, or until the first related publication or IP step (whichever comes first), may be applied to non-sensitive publishable datasets and code. Metadata should be made public immediately where possible.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

No special proprietary software should be required for the openly shared core outputs. Common tools will be sufficient, such as software that can read CSV/TSV, JSON/XML, TIFF/PNG, MP4, FCS and PDF/A files, and standard Python/Jupyter environments for code and analysis scripts. Where raw acquisition data depend on specialised instruments, publicly shared derivatives will be provided in open or widely used formats wherever possible.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Attribution-NoDerivatives 4.0

For openly shared datasets and documentation, CC BY 4.0 is recommended because it permits broad re-use with attribution. Where code is deposited separately, an open software license such as MIT may be used if more appropriate. Sensitive or restricted data will not be released under an open license.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-11-30

Quality assurance will include SOP-based workflows, validation protocols, traceability, internal checks and domain-specific QC procedures such as identity, viability, sterility, mycoplasma, endotoxin, potency and genetic stability checks where applicable. Version control, metadata review and documentation checks will be used for data and code.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Quality assurance will include SOP-based workflows, validation protocols, traceability, internal checks and domain-specific QC procedures such as identity, viability, sterility, mycoplasma, endotoxin, potency and genetic stability checks where applicable. Version control, metadata review and documentation checks will

be used for data and code.

e-use conditions will prohibit any attempt at re-identification of data subjects.

Citation of the dataset and compliance with license terms and ethics requirements will be expected from re-users.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

FAIR-enabling activities will be covered within the existing project work and RTU institutional infrastructure. No separate external FAIR-specific budget line is currently planned.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Janis Baronins (0000-0002-0831-2733)

Overall responsibility for data management will rest with Janis Baronins as PI. Experimental and stem-cell analytics data will be coordinated by Uldis Berzins. AI pipeline, scripts and technical integration data will be coordinated by Ilmars Viksne. Survey and market-research data and related documentation will be coordinated by Aija Rautmane and Inita Krumina, supported by Veranika Khlud. Cross-cutting analysis, reporting, release decisions and final oversight will remain with Janis Baronins.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Long-term public availability of non-sensitive outputs will rely on the selected public repository and RTU institutional retention practices. Retention of restricted data will be covered through institutional resources and/or follow-on projects as needed.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Passwords

- Physical access control

Data will be stored in access-controlled institutional systems such as RTU OneDrive for Business / RTU Teams and other approved environments. Personal and sample-linked data will be pseudonymised, separated from direct identifiers and shared on a need-to-know basis only. Backups, traceability, version control, internal audits, eTMF/LIMS-type documentation, data-processing agreements and privacy-by-design procedures will be applied. Public release will be limited to anonymised or otherwise non-sensitive outputs.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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